

Tactile Understanding: Word Evoking Image and Empathy

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Abstract

The mind's eye possesses the potential to be a vivid space in which, through the visualization of scenarios, people may be able to grow to relate to and understand that which was previously immaterial and misunderstood in simulated, imagined interaction with concrete information.

Museum visitors, most often, are not permitted to touch exhibited objects. *Feeling Without Touching (FWT)* is a design intervention into museum exhibits that is intended to heighten museum visitors' understandings of the tactile properties of selected objects—how it feels to use the objects—through guided visualization. The strategy employed in *FWT* is inspired by a notion that feeling (i.e. touch) may be linked with feeling (i.e. emotion). It seems that, perhaps, through an understanding of how it feels to use an object, visitors may be able to imagine how it feels to be the person who used the object.

The potential of visualization to provoke empathic response may be used by designers as a device to encourage audiences to perceive information as relevant and meaningful. Visualization activities developed by James L. Adams (1974) offer clues for prompting visualization, including the use of concrete, sensory-based language and the progressive establishment, manipulation and recombination of imagery.

Keywords: visualization, empathy, concrete language, tactile properties, relevance, experience, museum exhibition

Introduction

The mind's eye possesses the potential to be a vivid space in which, through the visualization of scenarios, people may be able to grow to relate to and understand that which was previously immaterial and misunderstood in simulated, imagined interaction with concrete information. The purpose of this paper is to describe a conceptual strategy and rationale for a design intervention into museum exhibitions that is intended to capitalize on the power of visualization to prompt critical thinking and empathy among museum visitors.

The strategy, titled, *Feeling Without Touching (FWT)*, seeks to heighten museum visitors' understandings of the tactile properties of selected objects—and how it feels to use the objects—through the experience of guided visualization. Here, the term “visualization” refers, in the traditional manner, to the formation of mental images, as related to imagination. It should be noted that this is in contrast with the use of the word “visualization” to mean, “to make visible,” which has been used in recent years to describe phenomena related to, for

example, the design of interfaces and the computer generated images of abstract concepts (Dictionary.com 2004).

Visualization as a device for communication

FWT developed through an opportunity that I encountered during the Fall of 2001, as a student in the Master of Graphic Design program at North Carolina State University, for consultation with the education department of the Smithsonian Institution, on the creation of a concept for intervention into museum exhibits. The scope of the resulting project, facilitated by Professor Meredith Davis through a course, titled, *Graphic Design as a Cultural Artifact*, was the development of a concept for a cost-effective graphic intervention system for possible implementation within existing exhibit spaces throughout the Smithsonian. The various objectives of the project sought to address a need to update information content among exhibits and inspire new and more active ways for visitors to participate in their experiences within the Smithsonian museums, as well as to prompt critical thinking.

Traditionally, museum visitors are most often not permitted, in any literal way, to touch exhibited objects—and for good reason. The damage that would occur inevitably through the handling of precious—and even less valuable—objects by the multitudes of people who visit Smithsonian museums each day would be regrettable. Nonetheless, it seems that, indeed, there may be some information that is important to know about objects that can only be understood through knowledge of and experience with the sensorial—including tactile—characteristics of the objects. Consequently, the circumstance of not being able to touch many and particular exhibited artifacts may regularly deny museum visitors some valuable insight gained only through a comprehension of the tactile properties (e.g. texture, weight, temperature, plasticity, etc.) of objects and the implications of those properties.

It appears, however, that imagination may be an effective device through which the visualization of activity can occur in the absence of actual activity. Visualization demonstrates considerable potential as an effective, nontraditional thinking tool that capitalizes on the “space” in the brain in which, it seems, simulated interaction with information may be experienced. According to James L. Adams (1974), it is possible for people to efficiently achieve full sensory experiences in their minds’ eyes through the stimulation of memory by means of concrete verbal cues used to evoke dynamic mental

images. Adams promotes the use of alternative thinking languages—visual thinking, in particular—for the evocation of creative thought in order to combat what he perceives as the stultifying Western bias toward, “...verbal languages [as] the basis of thinking.” Visual thinking, defined as a learning tool through which concrete information may be perceived and processed through seeing, imagining and drawing as a device for understanding, is an invaluable means of conceptualization (McKim 1980). Adams offers examples for the practical demonstration of how concrete language (i.e. “water coming to a boil on the stove”) might prompt visualization, actively engage the minds’ eye and help people to see and experience, in effect, various objects and scenarios “in action.”

Antonio Damasio (1999) refers to the phenomenon of visualization, as human beings experience it, as the “movie-in-the-brain.” He describes visualization in terms of its link with consciousness, as well as how visualization seems to serve as the domain within which the cognitive process of translating information acquired through sensory experiences into “mental patterns” transpires. Damasio’s proposition that the process of assembling sensory information into mental patterns—in the form of imagery—is the, “...highest [known] level of biological phenomenon,” speaks to the potential of the power and capacity of visualization.

It should be mentioned that, historically, there has been considerable conflict among the opinions of cognitive scientists in regard to the manner in which the phenomenon of visualization manifests itself in the human brain. Broadly, the factions that represent the viewpoints in opposition consist of scientists who support the “pictorial view” of visualization and, “...liken mental images to pictures,” as well as, by contrast, scientists who ascribe to the “descript ional view” of visualization and, “...liken [mental images] to linguistic descriptions.” For the purpose of elucidating the phenomenon of visualization for this paper, however, it may be enough to simply note that there seems to be some consensus of among cognitive scientists that, although, “...we [i.e. human beings] do not literally have pictures in our heads when we imagine things,” we do, indeed, possess the capacity to imagine (Tye 1991).

Borrowed from guided visualization activities developed by Adams (1974), the strategy behind *FWT* is a verbal one intended to amplify seeing, through which the tactile properties of objects are revealed via concrete, descriptive words. The intervention emphasizes the written word, but only as far as verbal language can be used as a vehicle through which words

function to evoke imagery in the mind's eye. It is our memory of "qualia"—the, "...simple sensory qualities," for instance, "in the relative blueness of the sky"—that is experienced during and lends specificity to visualization (Damasio 1999). Concrete language seems to be an effective means of triggering the memory of qualia, derived from previous experience with the world. It seems that it is the clarity of one's memory of the particular nature and characteristics of the qualia that may be associated with an object and/or scenario that determines the relative vividness of imagery and activity experienced during visualization (Adams 1974).

Concrete language includes those words that refer to some things, or characteristics of things, that are perceived through the senses. By contrast, abstract language refers to theories and concepts and, consequently, is not sensory-based or even particularly specific (McCarthy 1980). When one sets out to design a communication artifact intended to evoke mental images, it seems that it would only be to one's advantage to employ concrete language. At the very least, concrete language may limit the number of ways that a description can be interpreted. As an example, consider the words "beautiful flower." Although this description, indeed, possesses the capacity to prompt visualization, it seems unlikely that it would conjure up the same image in the minds of different people, due its lack of specificity. The more precise, concrete description, "ruby red zinnia with petals heavy and dripping with dew," however, seems to demonstrate a greater potential to efficiently direct the imagery that it evokes.

The structure of the guided visualization within *FWT* consists of three parts. According to Adams, it is not enough to simply present a description of an object, however vividly, and expect museum visitors to be able to "experience," in a fluid manner, how it feels to use the object. Instead, imagery must first become "flexible" and may be rendered so through the manipulation and recombination of the image's details. The first step of the three-part method involves the establishment of the details of the imagery (e.g. water in a pot being heated on a stove). Next, the details of the image are manipulated and recombined (e.g. "water coming to a boil"). Finally, the details of the image are manipulated and recombined again (e.g. water boiling over) and the image may now be considered flexible.

The scenarios described in *FWT* function as environments in which museum visitors might access unfamiliar information cast with familiar details. This method of relating new

information to existing knowledge is intended to establish the information as relevant and worthy of attention. According to Dan Sperber (1995), as a function of preservation, the human brain is wired to dismiss information that it does not perceive to be relevant. Consequently, for a person to be inclined to process new information, she must consider the information to be relevant and, therefore, meaningful.

The mental space in which visualization occurs seems to afford, in essence, a virtual environment in which people may experience simulated interaction with new and unfamiliar information, as well as the integration of new knowledge into their existing worldviews. In response to the vast potential of visualization as artificial experience, *FWT* addresses not only the revelation of the tactile properties of selected objects, but aims to promote an empathic understanding, among museum visitors, of the people who originally used the objects. This effort toward the exploration of what may be an addition of a potentially broader and socially relevant dimension to the intervention is rooted in a notion that perhaps feeling (i.e. touch) may be linked with feeling (i.e. emotion). In other words, if one understands how an object feels and is able to imagine how it feels to use the object, then perhaps she may begin to understand how it feels to be a person who used the object. It is hoped that insight gained through such an understanding may be a seed from which an empathic sensitivity toward people, experiences and the world may begin to develop among museum visitors.

Empathy is, "...the discipline of using one's imagination to see and feel as others see and feel" and involves, "... the ability to get inside another person's feelings and worldview." As described by Grant Wiggins and Jay McTighe (1998), one's capacity to empathize is indicative of a "mature understanding" of, and relationship with, the world. It seems that the empathic experience offered through the *FWT* intervention might enhance the meaning of objects and exhibitions for museum visitors and perhaps even contribute, more broadly, to visitors' understanding of humanity, in general.

The *Feeling Without Touching* demonstration project

The graphic program for the *FWT* intervention includes three parts, referred to here as *Strategies A, B* and *C*.

Figure 1, A magnetic, three-paneled, print-based graphic.

Strategy A consists of magnetic, three-paneled, print-based graphics designed to systematically develop museum visitors' understandings of the tactile properties of exhibited objects and the people who used the objects (Figure 1). Each graphic conveys a single scenario and is focused on a particular object (e.g. a wool blanket in a Civil War hospital). The content, which consists of descriptions of objects and scenarios in concrete language, structured in a form approaching that of poetry, develops in a sequence over the three panels, the purpose of which is to inspire flexibility in the imagery.

Figure 2, First panel of the three-paneled graphic.

The objective of the first panel in *Strategy A* is to spark the imagination of museum visitors (Figure 2). The verbal content of the panel consists of a simple two lines meant to establish an object in a scenario for visitors to begin to visualize (e.g. “I lay in bed/covered by this wool blanket.”).

In the second panel, two more lines of descriptive text are added (e.g. “*I lay in bed / each hour of the day / covered by this wool blanket / that is damp with my fevered sweat.*”) (Figure 3). Here, the words are meant to manipulate the visitors’ initial images of the object and scenario.

Figure 3, Second panel of the three-paneled graphic.

Two more lines of text are added in the third panel, so that the visitors’ impressions of the object and scenario may be manipulated even further (e.g. “*I lay in bed / each hour of the day / because I have a whole from a bullet in my abdomen / covered by this wool blanket / that is damp with my fevered sweat / and every time I shift brushes coarsely against my wound.*”) (Figure 4). Through the systematic transformation of imagery, visitors may grow to understand the tactile properties of the object and how it feels to use the object. It is intended that, by the third panel, visitors may develop empathy for the person who used the object.

Figure 4, Third panel of the three-paneled graphic.

Each panel has two incomplete sentences (i.e. “I feel _____.” And “The _____ is _____.”). These sentences serve as opportunities for museum visitors to express their understandings of the object, scenario and the person who used the object, by filling the blanks with magnetic words (i.e. magnets, printed with single concrete nouns or adjectives—for instance, “cold,” “wall” and “thin”—that may be removed and replaced on the graphics). These expressions are meant to be physical representations of visitors’ experiences. According to Richard Kimbell (1991), it seems that one’s comprehension of new information improves exponentially when she is able to give physical form to her thoughts. Individuals’ expressions may remain in place for other visitors to see. Additionally, all *Strategy A* graphics include an explanation of the purpose and objectives of the *FWT* intervention (e.g. “...By touching an object we can understand how it feels to use the object. If we were able to touch the objects in a museum, might we be able to understand the people better who used the objects, what their lives might have been like?”).

Strategy B consists of single-paneled, print-based graphics that feature progressive concrete, poetic descriptions of objects and scenarios (e.g. “Imagine the touch of / smooth crisp clothing / against your skin...” (Figure 5). The intention of *Strategy B* is that, through the facilitation of an understanding of what it feels like to be the person who used an object,

museum visitors may be able to make judgments in regard to the implications of associated social/cultural circumstances. The graphics for *Strategy B* could be printed on a dry-erase surface and include semantic differentials that refer to the content of the descriptive text, along which museum visitors may express their understandings of related social/cultural implications, circling numbers with a marker for others to see, in response to the question, “How do you feel?” (e.g. “poor/wealthy,” “greedy/generous”). The *Strategy B* graphics could also simply conclude with a question, for example, “Who are you?,” in order to prompt visitors to reflect, however passively, on what it would be like to be a person associated with an object and scenario.

Figure 5, A single-paneled, print-based graphic.

Strategy C consists of short video sequences, complete with sound and moving image, and represents an effort to capitalize on the potential of those elements to enhance museum visitors' understandings of the tactile properties of objects (Figure 6). Concrete, poetic language that describes an object and scenario is used in the video sequences to evoke visualization, just as it is in the print-based strategies, while sound and moving image offer greater opportunities for museum visitors to gain insight into how it might feel to be a person who used the object. The sequences are meant to run at a slow and meditative pace intended to inspire imagination, and should function as part of the exhibition environment, ideally projected largely on the walls behind the featured objects. The sound and moving images in the sequences should enhance, rather illustrate, the descriptive text, since visual information that is particularly specific may stifle visualization.

Figure 6, A frame from a video sequence.

Appropriate content for the *FWT* intervention could include any exhibited object that cannot be touched by museum visitors but of which tactile knowledge is critical for understanding how it feels to use the object. The content used within the demonstration project was derived from permanent exhibits at the North Carolina Museum of History, Raleigh.

FWT was designed to adapt to a variety of content and to be able to be implemented throughout a museum or system of museums or simply within a single exhibit. It seems that, perhaps, however, the greater the variety of contexts in which the intervention is featured might influence the impact that the intervention has on the development of empathic skill among museum visitors. Ideally, the graphics that support the intervention should be positioned in as close proximity as possible to the objects to which they refer. The *FWT*

strategies allow for both more thorough and abbreviated representations of the intervention as needed, in order to adjust to differences in the amount of space that may be available among museums and exhibits. For instance, *Strategy A*—the panels of which are five feet long—may be implemented when appropriate space is available. The smaller *Strategy B* graphics, however, may be used to accommodate environments with more limited space.

FWT employs a hierarchical information structure indicated by stylistic and spatial distinction among the typography. The visual hierarchy is intended to differentiate primary and supportive information, as well as reveal the progressive development of descriptive text across the graphic panels. Also, the manner in which the photographic images are handled suggests how museum visitors might use them as information. The photographs are brown-colored and monotone—reminiscent of sepia—and of various opacities. The decision to make the objects in the photographs appear less defined than they would in full-color is meant to support museum visitors in the application of their own imaginations to the photographs. The intention is that by downplaying detail, the photographs may be more supportive of, instead of a hindrance to, visualization.

Conclusion

The projected vision of successful use of the *FWT* intervention would include museum visitors reading, silently or aloud, descriptions of objects and scenarios as the concrete words evoke imagery in their minds' eyes. As the descriptions progress, the visitors would allow their understandings of the objects and scenarios to morph as the words manipulate their initial impressions. The visitors would arrive at a sense of being able to “feel” the objects in their minds, what it is like to use the objects and, then, eventually feel what it was like to be, and empathizing with, the people who used the objects.

Then, museum visitors would express their empathy by either selecting magnetic words to fill in the blanks of *Strategy A* or by making judgments within the semantic differentials of *Strategy B*. Perhaps these activities might even prompt discussion among museum visitors regarding, for instance, why particular word selections or judgments were made. Ideally, through interaction with *FWT*, museum visitors would learn how and continue, when appropriate, to consider objects on exhibit in museums in terms of the people who used them,

as opposed to as isolated objects on display. Both adults and children may participate in the *FWT* intervention, though, of course, at different cognitive levels.

The outcome of the development of the *FWT* intervention, in consultation with the Smithsonian Institution, is unknown. I presented *FWT* to the Smithsonian education department in November 2001. The response from the members of the department was favorable, particularly in regard to the potential of the intervention to prompt critical thinking and empathic skill among museum visitors and its perceived feasibility in terms of implementation. Subsequent to the presentation, I submitted a document to the education department that included a full explanation of the strategy, as well as visual examples of the demonstration graphics. However, though I have attempted contact, I have not heard from the education department since then. I am unaware of whether or not the *FWT* intervention, or any component thereof, has been implemented.

At this point, the strategy behind *FWT* is speculative. There is a good deal of observation and analysis to be done in terms of the evaluation of the effectiveness of the intervention in the fulfillment of its purpose—to reveal the tactile properties of objects through guided visualization in order to inspire empathy among museum visitors. In some way, I would like to arrange to observe people as they interact with the *FWT* demonstration project and to interview people in regard to their experiences with guided visualization. The *FWT* demonstration graphics need to be evaluated on the basis of their information structure and formal treatment, also. Stylistic and aesthetic decisions, in particular, have been made on a fairly intuitive basis.

Additionally, the strategies for guided visualization involved in this demonstration project have and will continue to be translated into some exploratory work that I have begun in the design of electronic media-based, interactive environments for learning.

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